

STUDENTS' TRANSLATION ABILITY IN ENGLISH TO INDONESIAN

R W Ningsih¹, H Triani², Y F Sihombing³

¹STKIP YPM Bangko

²Jambi University

sakti.rosadi@gmail.com , yosesihombing@yahoo.com

Abstract

This aims of this study was to analyze the ability of students to translate articles from English as source language to Indonesian as target language. Most of learners do not understand the proper use of words in translating articles from a foreign language as a source (English) to Indonesian as target language so that the meaning was generated becomes more complicated and confusing. This study was designed as a descriptive quantitative approach. The technique of sampling was total sampling; it was use a test to collect the data. This study showed that the student's translating ability is sufficient. The researcher expected some construction suggestions for the perfection forward, such as, English translation lecturers were expected to give the balancing of theory and practice in English translation course.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2582170

1. Introduction

English is known as foreign language that should be learnt by the people to understand the meaning of an English mean. It needs translation to comprehend it. Nida and Taber [1982, p. 12] state "translating consists in reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in term of style". It means that the translation has same term that is equivalence. The meaning, context, though, or message of both source of reproducing in the receptor language, the closest natural are equivalent to the message of source language. The first is meaning and secondly is style. The message of the source language should be equivalent. The reader of translation who knows the target language only will be confused if the target language is influenced by the source language. Meanwhile, a translated text should be transferring of the source language clearly. In order to make the clear meaning of source language, it is expected that the meaning of target language can be understood by the readers. So, a translated text should be readable. In the target language, readability is needed, because it makes the readers easier to catch the content of the translation text. Otherwise, when the translation text is not readable, it will make the readers difficult to understand the content of the text well.

The standard of competency in English translation course is the students able to translate sentences from source language to target language and how the process of translating itself with give attention to the translation theories and they could apply it to their translate task and last result, they able both translate well and communicative competence. The students can translate all of the kinds of the articles that given by the lecturer. Article sometimes was put on the magazine or newspaper. It can be a politic, social, economy, culture, technology, sport and education. Education article is the factual essay that gives the education information that happened in the world.

Translation is the general term referring to the transfer of thoughts and ideas from one language (source) to another (target), whether the languages are in written or oral form; whether the languages have established orthographies or do not have such standardization or whether one or both languages is based on signs, as with sign languages of the deaf, Brislin [cited in Suryawinata & Hariyanto 2003]. Translation is product or process changing source language in giving expression, rendering meaning and ideas, preserving semantic and stylistic equivalences to target language [Munday, 2001; Moentana, 2006; Bell, 1991; Nugroho, 2014]. It can say that translation is a process to change source language to target language that is done by translator without leaving the original message. The translator can use their own language and put all of imagination or their thinking while translating the text. Based on phenomenon above, it shows that the students did not understand what the text mean. They had limited vocabulary in English as a target language. They difficult to arrange the English words (TL) to Indonesian become complete sentences. They did not know how to translate the words and how to translate the meaning of the text. They were difficult to determine the equivalent based on the context and difficult to translate the sentences. This study was aimed to analyze students' ability in translate English article to Indonesian at sixth semester in English trainer at STKIP YPM Bangko. In order to achieve the objectives of this study, the question below was the limitations in this study. How the capability of students in translating articles English to Indonesian.

2. Literature Review

Translation

Translation is the ways of changes the source language to the target language so, it will make the students more understand about the English. According to Brislin [cited in Suryawinata and Hariyanto 2003, p. 12], "translation is the general term referring to the transfer of thoughts and ideas from one language (source) to another (target), whether the languages are in written or oral form; whether the languages have established orthographies or do not have such standardization or whether one or both languages is based on signs, as with sign languages of the deaf". In similar way, Munday [2001, p. 4] said that "the term translation itself has several meanings; it can refer to the general subject field, the product (the text that has been translated) or the process (the act of producing the translation, otherwise known as translating)."

According to Jakobson [cited in Munday 2001, p. 11], "translation divided into three categories. First, intralingua translation or "rewording": an interpretation of verbal signs by means of other signs of the same language. Second, interlingua translation or "translation proper": an interpretation of verbal signs by means of some other language, and the third, intersemiotic translation or "transmutation": an interpretation of verbal signs by means of signs of non-verbal sign systems". Suryawinata and Hariyanto [2003] told that intralingual translation is changing of a text to another text based on translator's interpretation and both of the text will write in same language. Interlingual translation is the translation in truth meaning. In this category, the translator writes back the meaning or message from source language into target language. Intersemiotic translation is an interpretation of a text into form or system other sign. Based on the statement above, this research will use the second category that is interlingual translation. It is process in changing from one language to the other language. English will be taken as a source language and Indonesia as a target language.

Translation is used by process, it means that a model to explain the thinking process that doing by a human when they did the translation. According to Bell [2001], the translation process is shown as follows.

Figure 1. Translation Process *Source: Bell. T. Roger*

This model shows that in extremely simplified form, the transformation of source language text into a target language text by means of processes: (1) the analysis of one language-specific text (the source language text) into a universal (non-language-specific) semantic representation and (2) the synthesis of that semantic representation into a second language specific text (the target language text).

Meaning

Meaning is the author message that wants to convey for the people. Nugroho [2014, p. 3] says that “Translation is not merely on meaning as a unit of lexical meaning. The process of rendering meaning involves some aspects as diction, grammatical structure, communication setting, and cultural context of the source text. Meaning of the source and target texts must be equivalent”. It should also be paid attention on the components embedded in a certain unit of meaning. By understanding the components of meaning of the source language expressions a translator can make the best decision related to the components. Meaning is also a written or spoken message from author that wants to say for the reader or listener. Nida (in Hatim and Munday, 2004:34), stated two kinds of linguistics meaning, they are referential meaning and connotative meaning. Nida [cited in Hatim & Munday 2004], said that referential meaning is known as denotation which deals with the words as signs or symbols. In similar way, Nida and Taber [1982] said that the words as symbols which refer to objects, events, abstracts, relations are known as referential meaning. Giving the meaning of a word referentially, a translator must be aware of any markers appears in the text. Based on Nugroho [2014, p. 5-6], “there are two markers that can be used to give meaning of words, syntactic marking and semotactic marking.”

3. Methodology

Research Design

This research used a descriptive quantitative approach. Descriptive research is concerned with conditions, practices, structures, differences or relationships that exist, opinion held processes that are going on or trends that are evident. Based on Arikunto [2010], descriptive research is the research was intended to observant the situation, condition or other, and the result is applied in research report form. In addition, Riyanto [2010], told that descriptive research is research that was aimed to give the indications, facts or

systematic and accurate events about population characteristics or certain region. Descriptive research do not look for or describe the correlation and hypothesis test. In similar way, Suryabrata [2012], the research means to make a description about situations or events.

The population of this research was divided into three classes at the sixth semester in English education program in semantics course; there were class A is 28 students, class B is 34 students and class C is 30 students so the number of population was 92 students.

The procedure in technique of collecting data were: firstly, the researcher gave the students a test. It was an English education article where an article was divided into five paragraphs. Secondly, gave the instruction, how to answer or translate the English education article. Thirdly, the researcher asked the students to answer or translate the English education article. Finally, the researcher collected all of students' answers sheet and analyzed the student's answer. This research had used an English education article as a test to measure the students' ability in English translation as instrument of this research. Technique of analyzing data would be done when all of data was collected. It was adopted from Waddington [cited in Khanmohammad & Osanlo, 2009].

4. Findings

Based on the students' result, it was concluded that the high qualification was located in B+, there were 5 students or 16,67% in range 78-82. Next, there were 20 students or 66,67% who got qualification C. The students failed were 5 students who got qualification E with 16,67% in range <48. So, there were 25 students successful in English translation but there were also 5 students who failed in this category. There was table 8 that showed the percentage in class C.

In this study, it used test to analyze the students' ability in English translation at the sixth semester in English education program of STKIP YPM Bangko academic year 2013/2014. The kind of test was achievement test, it was the test to measure the individual's ability after learned something. The researcher gave an English education article that was divided into three (3) paragraphs to the students. There were 92 students as population research. Twelve (12) students were absent, they were; class B= 4 students and class C= 8 students. So, the total of the students who were present and followed the test were 80 students.

Based on the students' values of English translation, the researcher found the difficulties that had found by the sample was in translating the meaning from English into Indonesia. Mostly the students were wrong in this sentences; 1) for any unit you start in your ESL class there will most likely be a group of words that students must memorize, 2) the words should be spread out and written in large print, 3) instead of short concise lists, you want words all over the place in no discernable order, 4) he is now going to pick one of the words in his head, 5) the two competing students will attempt to point to the circled word that fits the meaning they just heard, 6) students may get loud.

5. Conclusion

Based on the study that has been done to the students at the sixth semester in English Education Program of STKIP YPM Bangko in Academic Year 2013/2014, the researcher concluded that there were 50 students successful in English translation about 62,5% and there were 30 students were fail or 37,5% from 80 students. The students who got qualification A was 1 student, B+ were 11 students, C were 38 students, and E were 30 students. From the data that provided and showed in each classes, such as; A, A-, B+, B, B-, C+, C, C-, D, E, mostly the students got qualification C in range 58-62. So, it can be concluded

that the students' ability in English translation at the sixth semester in English education program of STKIP YPM Bangko was adequate.

References

- [1] Bell R T 1991 *Translation and Translating: Theory and Practice* (England: Longman Group UK Limited)
- [2] Hatim B dan Munday J 2004 *Translation: An Advanced Resource Book* (Ed) (Routledge: Candlin, C. N & Carter, Ronald)
- [3] Khanmohammad H and Osanloo M 2009 Moving toward Objective Scoring *A Rubric for Translation Assessment 1* 1 138
- [4] Munday J 2001 *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and applications* (London: Routledge)
- [5] Nida B A and Taber C R 1982 *The Theory and Practice of Translation* (Leiden: E.J. Brill)
- [6] Nugroho B A 2014 *Meaning and Translation* (Yogyakarta: English Department of the Faculty of Languages and Arts of Yogyakarta State University)
- [7] Suryawinata Z and Hariyanto S 2003 *Translation (Bahasan Teori dan Penuntun Praktis Menerjemahkan)* (Yogyakarta: Kanisius)

